

Applying Federated Learning on Decentralized Smart Farming: A Case Study

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Abstract—In the field of Smart Agriculture, accurate time series forecasting is essential for farmers to gather and evaluate relevant information about various aspects of their work, such as the management of harvests, livestock, crops, water and soil. One commonly used method for trend forecasting in time series is the Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) model, due to its ability to retain context for longer periods and enhance performance in context-intensive tasks. To further improve the results, the use of Federated Learning (FL) can be implemented, allowing multiple data providers to simultaneously train on a shared model while preserving data privacy. In this study, a Centralised Federated Learning System (CFLS) is leveraged, that implements and evaluates the efficacy of FL in smart agriculture through the use of datasets produced by such infrastructures. The system receives data from multiple clients and creates an optimised global model through model federation. Consequently, the federated approach is compared with the conventional local training to explore the potential of FL in real-time forecasting for the Smart Farming sector.

Index Terms—Federated Learning, Deep Learning, LSTM, Smart farming, Forecasting, Crop Optimisation, Animal Welfare, Synthetic Data, Dataset

I. INTRODUCTION

In order to build a dependable AI model in the field of Machine Learning (ML), data from multiple sources are often required. This approach's variability improves the model's predictive abilities by training it on a wider range of patterns. However, this comes with several disadvantages and dangers, the main one being a lack of privacy. The datasets of each source must all be uploaded to the same server. This strictly local ML method, whether intentionally or unintentionally, presents the possibility of sensitive information being leaked.

To that end, a new sub-field of ML, known as Federated Learning (FL) [1] was developed. The term was first introduced by Google [2] and it was utilised early on for next-word prediction on mobile devices [3]. In the following years since then, it has expanded to a variety of ML fields. A framework implemented with FL in mind can train a model through a

more private approach, without independent data providers having to actually share raw information, thus eliminating the problem of otherwise private data being exposed to third parties. FL can also be applied to ease the burden on other tasks, such as handling large amounts of data more efficiently, or supervised training [4][5].

To produce a solid comparative study of the performance of local and FL model training on the decentralised agricultural data, this work produced and utilised a Centralised Federated Learning System (CFLS). The goal of the implementation of this system is to be able to experiment on the local and FL training, keeping constant the same hyperparameters for all models and nodes in the duration of one experiment, instead of manually configuring every node separately.

Although several DL approaches were considered and utilised once the system had been established, initial experiments were carried out using LSTM models, and the current paper focuses exclusively on them. The reason for selecting LSTMs is their long-short term memory retaining ability, giving them an excellent reputation as a State-of-the-Art technique for time series prediction, which is the required forecasting method for Smart Farming. The system is trained upon data received from federated clients, and for each one, it builds two models, a local and a federated one in order to perform an in-depth comparative analysis of their performance. Based on the aforementioned, this work offers the following contributions:

- A Federated methodology for building optimised forecasting models in Smart Agriculture applications
- A comparison between conventional Deep and Federated models in various Smart agriculture use cases.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section II showcases a collection of established works regarding FL and LSTM models. Section III explains the adopted methodology and also defines LSTM and FL in greater detail. The process followed in order to optimize the LSTM model for each dataset will also be provided. Subsequently, Section IV outlines the evaluation process of the experiments conducted, showcases the datasets that were utilised and analyzes the experiment results properly. Each experiment generates predictions from the local and federated models of every node, enabling a comparison of the two approaches for each instance. The paper is concluded in Section V.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The potential danger presented by data leakage has made direct data exchange between clients not only unreliable but

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also prohibited. Due to this, FL has gained significant traction by researchers in recent years. Early on, this new method of machine learning was adapted for mobile devices [3], [6].

There have been notable attempts to exploit the benefits of FL with forecasting tasks since then, such as with traffic flow prediction [7], or the proposal by Taik et al. concerning Electrical Load Forecasting [4]. In [8], FL is also implemented on data obtained from smart meters for load forecasting.

FL has also been gaining popularity in more closely related subject matters to this paper, with Manoj et al. [9] practicing and analyzing an FL focused method for soybean yield forecasting. Amiri et al [10] proposed approaches for further enhancing information privacy in Smart Farming [11]. Saha et al. [12] introduces a data-centric client selection technique which enhances the viability of FL across distributed edge networks.

Over time, several types of ML models dedicated to the forecasting of time series have been implemented [13], many of them still being actively employed in a number of scientific fields. Liu et al. have utilised LSTM models for classification purposes in time series forecasting [14].

Long-term time series data can often exhibit a more heterogeneous form, which presents challenges when it comes to FL, especially if updates to each local dataset are applied through it. Díaz González proposed Federated Clustering [15] in order to address this problem. The study in [16] explores the effectiveness of various Asynchronous Federated Learning (AFL) applications with diverse data.

As the scope of an FL framework increases, so does the communication bandwidth between devices. However, much of the gradient exchange is unnecessary and becomes redundant with the addition of FL. In response, the authors of [17] proposed two methods to combat this: Federated Distillation (FD) and Federated Augmentation (FAug).

Additional work by Liu et al [18] utilizing FL with time series data, introduces a framework indented for anomaly detection in the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) field, while also assisting in making FL more communication-efficient. The process of anomaly detection is carried out through a CNN-LSTM model. Yu et al. recently proposed a Federated LSTM system for defending Intelligent Connected Vehicles against network intrusion threats [19] through message ID prediction. A framework like this can potentially not only protect the affected vehicle but also any nearby vehicle also connected to the same network. Another recent publication concerns FedServ [20], which aims at the latency associated with vehicle task service.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Preprocessing

While implementation and optimization of the neural network itself are both vital in an ML task, in practice the network's predictive abilities are also heavily impacted by the form in which it receives the data. Efficient data preprocessing [21] is equally crucial to model building.

Preprocessing refers to a number of techniques used to adjust the provided data for the needs of the task at hand. Most often, the raw data are insufficient and require editing before they can be used in a model. Both something as trivial as adjusting the dates in a csv file to an appropriate format, as well as something like the handling of imbalanced datasets [22] are considered preprocessing steps.

In this paper, the preprocessing procedure followed a similar pattern for each dataset: For starters, all available data belong to the time series category, therefore resampling is required. Resampling is the act of modifying the time series observations frequency. For example, a dataset that contains information from daily weather reports can be sampled down to weekly batches. The reverse is also possible, with new entries being created by up-sampling the available ones when needed. However, this requires some additional care as the new data that are generated need to have realistic values. This can be achieved through data interpolation, which is able to generate believable values to fill in the newly created gaps. For the scope of this paper though, up-sampling was not utilised.

A common occasion is missing values, meaning features in certain entries that are simply blank. Although a selection of techniques to handle this problem exist, in the case at hand, they are replaced using forward filling [23], a popular method that copies the previous value into the missing one. In the event that some missing values still remain afterwards, they are replaced with zero. This allows us to continue, without having to drop the entire row due to the one blank feature, while it could still contain valuable information. All remaining data are scaled into the $[0, 1]$ range. This helps close the distance between data points, improving overall model performance. After the completion of scaling, the training phase is initiated.

B. Long Short Term Memory Models

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) are renowned for their capability in handling sequential and time series data, owing to their capacity for maintaining and applying context during prediction. However, the memory of RNNs is strictly short-term and they start to under-perform when the context is required for longer strings of data.

A popular variation of RNNs, Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) models [24] are designed in an attempt to mitigate the former's memory issues and make context handling more manageable. LSTMs aim to retain significant data sequences in their short-term memory, such as key words in a sentence, for extended periods while discarding irrelevant information.

In Figure 1, the process LSTMs undertake is showcased. The top line represents the short-term memory where important information is stored, named the Cell State (C_{t-1} , C_t). In the bottom line, the input (x_t) is observed, as well as the hidden state which is also common to other model types (h_{t-1} , h_t). A single LSTM cell receives the input, as well as the previous hidden state and cell state, then it passes them through a series of gates, specifically a) the forget gate (f_t), b) the input gate (g_t) and c) the output gate (o_t). Once done processing, the LSTM cell outputs an updated hidden state and cell state.

Fig. 1: LSTM Cell Architecture

The forget gate dictates which information, both recent and old, is saved and which is discarded. This includes both the cell state and the hidden state from the previous loop, as well as the present status. In Eq. (1) mathematical formula for the forget gate is presented. The input x_t and the previous hidden state h_{t-1} are passed into a sigmoid function, represented by σ . The output is a vector of the same size as C_{t-1} , with values between 0 and 1. The number 0 denotes that all prior knowledge has been forgotten, while the number 1 represents the complete preservation of past information. Additionally, b and W stand for the cyclic weights of bias and forgotten gates [14] for both this and the following equations.

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f) \quad (1)$$

The input gate measures the current input value to determine the amount required to solve the task. The process has two steps, the first, shown in Eq. (2), uses a sigmoid layer to decide which values to keep, 0 or 1. The second step is a tanh layer, as presented in Eq. (3), assigning importance values to the kept data by adding weights to them.

$$g_t = \sigma(W_g[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_g) \quad (2)$$

$$\tilde{C}_t = \tanh(W_S[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_S) \quad (3)$$

Next, the information deemed useful by the input gate is added to the cell state C_t , as illustrated in Eq. (4), and becomes the updated cell state that is used going forward.

$$C_t = f_t C_{t-1} + g_t \tilde{C}_t \quad (4)$$

The output gate selects values to output, hence the name. Once again, the process is two-fold. First, a sigmoid layer is executed to decide what data can come through, as shown in Eq. (5). The updated cell state is resampled to $[-1, 1]$ using a tanh layer and multiplied by the sigmoid output, according to Eq. (6). This process is realized in the new hidden state h_t .

$$o_t = \sigma(W_o[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o) \quad (5)$$

$$h_t = \tanh(C_t) o_t \quad (6)$$

Fig. 2: Federated Learning Architecture

The output's nature is task-dependent, such as a word that matches or improves the meaning of a given sentence.

C. Federated Learning

Traditional DL techniques require the transportation of vital private information between end-user infrastructures as all available data need to be gathered into a single point of aggregation, i.e., a central server in order to be trained locally. This often violates data confidentiality regulations and exposes the aforementioned sensitive information to data leakage [25]. FL represents an alternative strategy, designed to address this problem. The training is dispersed across various computer systems, often referred to as clients or nodes. Instead of raw data, nodes send their local model updates, trained on that local data, to the aggregator, thus avoiding possible leakage.

Figure 2 depicts the logic behind the procedure, and the steps are as follows: First, the nodes receive the initial model from the server. The nodes improve the model they received by training it on their local datasets for a given number of iterations. These updates are short-lived and are never stored. The updated model parameters are sent to the server to build a new model. Any weight changes are also processed in memory and are deleted after aggregation. The server's updated model is distributed to the nodes again and the process is repeated until the target forecast accuracy is achieved.

It is worth noting other use cases where FL can prove useful, some of which include the possibility of different datasets not being evenly distributed, making the implementation of more diverse data possible, or its contribution in processing larger amounts of data faster [4]. One of the most important aspects of FL however is the resource optimisation that the lack of data transportation brings. This helps avoid network bottlenecks and heavy-duty processing by the intermediate parties.

D. Hyperparameter Tuning

Optimizing an LSTM model in order to reach peak performance can be a time-consuming problem, one that some

Time	Feature A	Feature B	Feature C	Target
0	a0	b0	c0	T0
1	a1	b1	c1	T1
2	a2	b2	c2	T2
3	a3	b3	c3	T3
4	a4	b4	c4	T4
5				T5
6				
7				
...				
n				

Fig. 3: Time Series Lookback

researchers [26] support that can be resolved via hyperparameter tuning. As the name indicates, it is the process of selecting a set of ideal hyperparameters for a neural network, allowing models to operate at their best. This is something that can be done manually with repetitive testing, but the work can also be automated using a variety of techniques. In this paper, the technique chosen is Keras Tuner, a library that is a component of Tensorflow [27], which allows the optimization of any subtotal of hyperparameters.

More precisely, when constructing a model, a hyperparameter can be tuned using Keras Tuner to select a value from a provided list instead of using a static value. If the intended values for the hyperparameters are numerical, minimum, maximum, and step values can be set, e.g., choosing anything from 8 to 24 with a step of 8 generates the following list: [8, 16, 24]. Keras Tuner will run a model several times, testing out various hyperparameter combinations. The models' performances can be ranked based on a selected metric, such as loss. For the LSTM models in this paper, the hyperparameters chosen using Keras Tuner were the node amount in non-initial layers, the learning rate and the loss method.

Additionally, the number of epochs and the lookback were tested with variable values manually. Although Keras Tuner could have selected those hyperparameters too, it was decided to test them using the same number of epochs and lookback during an entire iteration. For clarification, lookback refers to a feature exclusive to time series forecasts. It is the x number of previous timesteps, which are utilised to predict the following timestep. An alternative name for lookback is window. The process can be viewed in Figure 3, where the values of the previous five training and target features are taken into consideration in order to predict the upcoming target. Other hyperparameters, such as dropout or decay rate were considered as well, but were dropped due to not observing any significant changes upon testing.

IV. EVALUATION

A. Datasets

The datasets utilised concern the field of Smart Farming. They are split into two categories, each containing multiple datasets that originated from different nodes collecting data.

1) *Farm Animal Welfare*: The first category, contains temporal data gathered from sensor readings within a stable. It has roughly 80000 data samples split into two nodes. The intent is

to use the provided sensor data in order to predict future stable conditions and to secure the welfare of the animals housed in these stables. Table I can be referred to for more details, where the Features row lists all of its features, while the Target row specifies the forecasting mark of interest. In addition, a batch of synthetically generated datasets were also utilised for this category. This was done to help the model create a better generalization by providing augmented data [28]. The real and synthetic datasets were treated as separate dependencies. In Table II more details are provided regarding the synthetic data.

2) *Animal Feed Cultivation*: This second category contains historical sensor data for field-deployed sensors in different remote locations, by distinct federated nodes. These sensors overview the conditions in a variety of crops and plantations (fields) of decentralised agricultural infrastructures. One significant feature of this dataset is that the distribution between its six nodes is uneven. These datasets are utilised to predict future field conditions using past values, with the aim of helping the farmer optimize crop production and reduce production costs. Table III presents the respective details.

B. Evaluation Metrics

The LSTM models' predictions were evaluated against the real values of the datasets using a number of metrics in order to decide the best one. The metrics that remained valid throughout the experiment cycle are listed below. In the following equations, T_i represents the true values and P_i represents the model predictions, while n is the number of data points.

1) *Mean Absolute Error (MAE)*: The aggregated mean of the errors between the real and the predicted values. Popular due to making the difference between them easy to interpret.

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |T_i - P_i| \quad (7)$$

TABLE I: Animal Welfare Dataset Information

Farm Animal Welfare	
Features	DateTime, Air Humidity, Air Temperature, Ch4, CO2 Avg, CO2 Max, CO2 Min, Counter, Dew Point Temperature
Target	CO2 Avg
Records	>80K
Nodes	2

TABLE II: Animal Welfare (Synthetic) Dataset Information

Farm Animal Welfare	
Features	DateTime, Air Humidity, Air Temperature, Ch4, CO2 Avg
Target	CO2 Avg
Records	>80K
Nodes	5

TABLE III: Animal Feed Cultivation Dataset Information

Animal Feed Cultivation	
Features	DateTime, Air Humidity, Air Pressure, Air Temperature, Battery, Counter, Dew Point Temp, Volumetric WC, Soil Temp
Target	Air Humidity
Records	>3M
Nodes	6

2) *Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE)*: Measures forecasting system accuracy as a percentage. Easy to understand, but may output infinity in cases with minimal errors.

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|T_i - P_i|}{T_i} \quad (8)$$

3) *Mean Square Error (MSE)*: Computes the average squared deviation between predicted and true values, with zero indicating no error in the model.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (T_i - P_i)^2 \quad (9)$$

4) *Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)*: Square root of MSE, can be interpreted directly as it is in the same units as the response variable, making it a popular evaluation measure.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (T_i - P_i)^2} \quad (10)$$

C. Experiment Results

Figures 4, 5 and 6 visualize the RMSE evaluation for each category. Specifically, the graphs showcase the loss, meaning the difference between the real and the forecasting values of each node for both the local and federated models. Based on those figures, it can be concluded that the federated models perform comparably well to their local counterparts.

The clean numerical outputs for RMSE, as well as the rest of the metrics, are shown in Tables IV, V and VI, further displaying what was stated above. The loss metric is found to be acceptably low in most cases. Furthermore, both iterations of the Farm Animal Welfare data have shown generally superior outcomes using the federated model. This type of outcome could potentially be replicated for the Animal Feed Cultivation data as well with additional model optimization.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Federated Learning presents itself as a valuable feature, that can assist in optimising model performance. Additional benefits include the potential for increased data diversity, as well as conserving resources when handling large datasets and making predictions, allowing the latter to happen in real-time. This paper performs a comparative study of two approaches, namely, local and Federated Learning, evaluating their performance on federated agricultural time series-based data. The proposed methodology relies on a developed experimental system, incorporating modern DL models, like LSTMs, to realise the performance analysis of the realised experiments, comparing the two approaches to evaluate their relative reliability. Results showcased that the federated models can provide superior results than the locally trained models, a fact that lies on the mutual knowledge obtained by the model federation.

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Fig. 4: Animal Welfare Evaluation Graph

Fig. 5: Animal Welfare (Synthetic) Evaluation Graph

Fig. 6: Animal Feed Cultivation Evaluation Graph

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TABLE IV: Animal Welfare Loss Collection

ANIMAL WELFARE DATASET								
	RMSE		MSE		MAE		MAPE	
	Local	Federated	Local	Federated	Local	Federated	Local	Federated
Node0	0.0213	0.0154	0.0005	0.0002	0.0170	0.0109	4.22	2.44
Node1	0.0286	0.0276	0.0008	0.0008	0.0165	0.0165	5.16	5.35
Average	0.0249	0.0215	0.0006	0.0005	0.0168	0.0137	4.69	3.895

TABLE V: Animal Welfare (Synthetic) Loss Collection

ANIMAL WELFARE DATASET – SYNTHETIC								
	RMSE		MSE		MAE		MAPE	
	Local	Federated	Local	Federated	Local	Federated	Local	Federated
Node0	0.0691	0.0466	0.0048	0.0022	0.0538	0.0379	608.83	215.71
Node1	0.1488	0.053	0.0221	0.0028	0.1396	0.0458	1357.15	432.37
Node2	0.0771	0.043	0.0059	0.0019	0.063	0.0341	419.59	179.88
Node3	0.1014	0.0478	0.0103	0.0023	0.0896	0.0406	1414.13	2587.66
Node4	0.1029	0.0402	0.0106	0.0016	0.0869	0.0322	437.25	223.5
Average	0.0999	0.0461	0.0107	0.0021	0.0866	0.0381	847.39	727.824

TABLE VI: Animal Feed Cultivation Loss Collection

ANIMAL FEED CULTIVATION DATASET								
	RMSE		MSE		MAE		MAPE	
	Local	Federated	Local	Federated	Local	Federated	Local	Federated
Node0	0.0243	0.0411	0.0006	0.0017	0.0187	0.0331	1.92	3.21
Node1	0.0505	0.0367	0.0025	0.0013	0.0423	0.028	4.44	2.93
Node2	0.0172	0.0184	0.0003	0.0003	0.0124	0.0134	2.23	2.45
Node3	0.0150	0.0140	0.0002	0.0002	0.0114	0.0106	1.61	1.5
Node4	0.0170	0.0293	0.0003	0.0009	0.0117	0.0231	2.31	4.96
Node5	0.0203	0.0405	0.0004	0.0016	0.0134	0.0351	3.68	10.77
Average	0.0241	0.03	0.0007	0.001	0.0183	0.0239	2.6983	4.3033

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